

Ultra-wide Band LNAs for BRAND Front-ends: Single-ended and Balanced Approaches

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Change Record

Revision	Date	Affected Paragraphs(s)	Reason/Initiation/Remarks
Preliminary	2018-02-12	All	First Issue
A	2018-02-26	New section “Balanced amplifier with improved 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrid couplers”. Changes in the conclusion section.	Included data of balanced amplifiers with new 5 stages 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrids.
B	2020-06-18	Cover	Removed confidential warning

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Introduction

This report presents the results of several ultra-wide band cryogenic low noise amplifiers designed, fabricated and tested by Yebes Observatory in the framework of BRAND EVN (Broad Band EVN) project. The ultimate goal of BRAND is to develop a prototype broad-band digital receiver for the EVN¹ antennae, covering a one decade frequency range, from 1.5 GHz to 15.5 GHz. Yebes amplifiers will be used as front-end LNAs and shall ultimately cover the whole 1.5-15.5 GHz band with the best possible performance.

The design of a low noise amplifier for such a wide band is a challenge. It is not possible to optimize simultaneously the noise temperature and the input reflection and there is a severe tradeoff between these two parameters, especially at the lower end of the band. As a result, the input return loss is usually poor at low frequencies. The return loss of wide band feeds suffer from similar restrictions and the mismatch between these two elements could lead to practical problems in the receiver, like high ripples in the noise power. Cryogenic isolators could solve this problem but are only available for narrower bands.

A balanced amplifier configuration is a practical alternative with several advantages. It comprises two 3 dB 90° hybrid couplers, two LNAs and a couple of matched loads assembled according to Fig. 1. If hybrids with low unbalance are used, the input and output reflection of the balanced amplifier depend on the return losses of the input and output hybrids respectively, and the noise temperature is approximately that of a single amplifier degraded by the insertion loss of the input hybrid. Therefore, counting with good hybrids, it is possible to obtain an LNA with low input reflection and noise temperature simultaneously. An additional benefit of the balanced configuration is the improvement of the linearity range in 3 dB. The drawbacks are the aforementioned noise penalty and the increase of cost, complexity, size and power consumption.

Figure 1: *Balanced amplifier schematic*

The aim of this report is to compare the performance of the different alternatives in order to take an informed decision about the best LNA for BRAND. The following sections present the cryogenic measurements of different LNAs. Further work is still ongoing to improve the balanced amplifier results.

A description of the final amplifier, details about its design and operational procedures will be given in a separate report delivered with each unit. Details about the measurement procedures will also be included in it and can be found in [1] and [2].

¹European VLBI network

Wide Band single-ended LNA

YebeS LNA group has developed a wide band amplifier for the next generation of VGOS² geodetic receivers which has already been tested successfully in its RAEGE³ antenna. It is a small sized hybrid design which allows the use of transistors of diverse technologies on each amplification stage to improve different characteristics of the performance.

Figure 2: External view of the Y214G 1 cryogenic LNA. Dimensions excluding connectors are 20×22×9 mm (X×Y×Z in the picture).

The new version of this LNA for this project includes top-performance InP transistors from ETH⁴ in the first stage, which yield an average **noise temperature** in the band of **6.5 K**. InP transistors from HRL⁵ are used in the second stage. The third stage incorporates commercial GaAs transistors from Mitsubishi, which are much better in terms of **linearity** and yield a 1 dB compression point at the input better than **-30 dBm**. This is especially important in applications like BRAND, very sensitive and vulnerable to radio-interference, which could easily saturate the amplifier and ruin its performance in the whole band.

Output reflection is better than **-15 dB** across the band, but the input reflection suffer from the limitations of these low noise designs and is higher than **-10 dB** in the lower half of the band.

Each stage is biased independently to optimize the characteristics of each transistor.

Several units were fabricated and tested and are ready to be delivered. The results of the pair of amplifiers used in the balanced configurations of the next sections are shown in figures 3 and 4.

² VLBI Global Observing System, formerly VLBI2010

³ Red Atlántica de Estaciones Geodinámicas y Espaciales

⁴ InP HEMT technology group (Microwave Electronics group) of the IFH at the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, Zurich (ETHZ).

⁵ Hughes Research Laboratories

Figure 3: Cryogenic noise and gain of wide band amplifiers Y214G 1016 and Y214G 1018. Measurements taken at 15 K.

Figure 4: Cryogenic input and output return loss of wide band amplifiers Y214G 1016 and Y214G 1018. Measurements taken at 15 K.

Balanced amplifier with 2-14 GHz hybrid couplers

The first approach design to a wide band balanced configuration used a 2-14 GHz 3-dB 90° cryogenic hybrid, designed and manufactured at Yebes for VGOS geodetic receivers. It was also successfully tested in the field as part of a balanced amplifier in a RAEGE antenna, alongside with the single amplifier mentioned in the previous section. It is a coupled line structure in stripline technology using five $\lambda/4$ sections, based on a design with just three sections for the 4-12 GHz band [3], with excellent phase and amplitude unbalanced and low insertion loss.

Figure 5: External view of one of the cryogenic 3dB 90° hybrids used in the 2-14 GHz balanced amplifier. An assembled amplifier can be seen in Figure 12.

Two complete balanced amplifiers were assembled and tested for this project with similar results. The data of one of them is presented in figures 6 and 7 compared with the data from one of the single-ended amplifiers (Y214G 1016). Note the slight degradation in noise (less than 1 K in the band) and the radical improvement of the return loss. The 1 dB compression point at the input is around -26 dBm.

Figure 6: Cryogenic noise and gain of a balanced amplifier (in red) with 2-14 GHz hybrid couplers. Measurements of the single amplifiers are in Fig. 3. One of them is shown here (in blue) for reference. Data taken at 15 K.

Figure 7: Cryogenic input and output return loss of a balanced amplifier (in red) with 2-14 GHz hybrid couplers. Measurements of the single amplifiers are in Fig. 4. One of them is shown here (in blue) for reference. Data taken at 15 K.

Balanced amplifier with 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrid couplers

A new 1.5-15.5 GHz 3-dB 90° cryogenic hybrid was designed and manufactured at Yebes for this project. Like the previous one it is a coupled line structure in stripline technology, but it comprises seven $\lambda/4$ sections to get the whole band covered with the lowest unbalance. This number of sections results in higher insertion losses, and as a consequence of the bandwidth increase (one decade), there is a degradation of the unbalance.

Two complete balanced amplifiers were assembled and tested for this project with similar results. The data of one of them is presented in figures 8 and 9 compared with the data from one of the single-ended amplifiers (Y214G 1016). The noise degradation is higher (more than 2 K) and there is a significant ripple in gain and noise due in part to the hybrid unbalance. The return loss is lower than -15 dB for more than 95% of the band. The 1 dB compression point at the input is around -26 dBm.

Figure 8: Cryogenic noise and gain of a balanced amplifier (in red) with 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrid couplers. Measurements of the single amplifiers are in Fig. 3. One of them is shown here (in blue) for reference. Data taken at 15 K.

Figure 9: Cryogenic input and output return loss of a balanced amplifier (in red) with 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrid couplers. Measurements of the single amplifiers are in Fig. 4. One of them is shown here (in blue) for reference. Data taken at 15 K.

Balanced amplifier with improved 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrid couplers

A second version of 1.5-15.5 GHz 3-dB 90° cryogenic hybrid was designed and manufactured at Yebes for this project. This time it was based on the 2-14 GHz one, with five $\lambda/4$ sections (not seven, like the previous 1.5-15.5 GHz design), but trying to stretch the band as far as possible

at the expense of a poorer unbalance. This design provides better insertion losses and reflection.

A balanced amplifier was assembled and tested for this project. Its data is presented in figures 10 and 11 compared with the data from one of the single-ended amplifiers (Y214G 1016). The noise degradation is around 1.5 K, clearly better than the previous balanced version, and with very low ripple as in the 2-14 GHz version. There is also an improvement in the reflection, with the input return loss only higher than -15 dB below 1.7 GHz.

Figure 10: Cryogenic noise and gain of a balanced amplifier (in red) with **improved** 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrid couplers. Measurements of the single amplifiers are in Fig. 3. One of them is shown here (in blue) for reference. Data taken at 15 K.

Figure 11: Cryogenic input and output return loss of a balanced amplifier (in red) with *improved* 1.5-15.5 GHz hybrid couplers. Measurements of the single amplifiers are in Fig. 4. One of them is shown here (in blue) for reference. Data taken at 15 K.

Figure 12: Top and side views of a balanced amplifier in the Dewar, testing noise temperature. The amplifier is framed in a red box in the left picture.

Conclusions and future work

- A single-ended amplifier (Y214G 1) has been designed and several units have been tested with good results in noise and linearity. The input reflection is higher than -10 dB below 8 GHz and this could lead to ripples in the receiver response.
- Three versions of a balanced amplifier using Y214G 1 LNAs and Yebes designed hybrid couplers have been tested. Their advantages over a single amplifier are clear: a huge improvement of the input reflection and a 3 dB higher linearity range.
- The limitations of the balanced amplifiers are imposed by the hybrid couplers used. The first design degrades the noise temperature by less than 1 K, but only covers the band up to 14.5 GHz. The second design covers the whole band, but degrades the noise temperature more than 2 K and introduces ripples in gain and noise. The third

design also covers the whole band with just a slight deterioration at the noise high end and IRL low end, and a penalty of 1.5 K in noise temperature. A comparison of noise and IRL of all designs is shown in figures 13 and 14.

- It would be very instructive to model the impact of the different amplifier designs in the performance of a receiver front-end. To do so, we would just need to know the scattering parameters of the set (feed, cable) connected to the amplifier input.

Figure 13: Cryogenic noise of a single LNA (black) and the three balanced amplifiers developed. Data taken at 15 K.

Figure 14: Cryogenic input return loss of a single LNA (black) and the three balanced amplifiers developed. Data taken at 15 K.

References

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